

Sustainable Agricultural Practices and Rural Economy in Odisha : A Lesson from Adivasis Communities

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Abstract :- Are sustainable agriculture and rural development possible? Yes, it is possible among the Adivasis communities. As they are the protector, safeguard, and security for jungle, jal, and jamin. They sustain their way of agriculture and show society how one should be sustainable always. Thus, the study objectively looking forward to observing the changing pattern of agriculture among the Adivasis communities. Among them, indigenous knowledge about agriculture, simple technology, skills and use of manure on land, preservation of seeds, conserving the jungle, and protecting the animals are seen. Thus, the knowledge among them is transferable from one generation to another. The scholarship also sees the cultural, and belief-based society which is interconnected with their agriculture, livelihood, and life pattern. The study also looks at their preservation pattern of seeds, roots, leaves, and foods among them, and how it is sustainable for the next year to come. Again study looks through their types of agriculture that are practiced among them. The study also sees the use of technology in agriculture that always keeps the land fertile and better for farming. Further, the study also looks at the use of manure that keeps the land fertile and crops grow better, and harvest good fold of crops. Overall, when Adivasis' techniques, knowledge, preservation, and conservation patterns are used – it fetches the sustainable development process in agriculture and it develops the rural economy subsistence and self-sufficiency. Although Adivasis' way of agriculture is not profit-oriented it is sustainable, good for life, better for land, and provides maximum nutrients and protein from the foods. Thus, the study tries to elaborate, critically analyze modern versus traditional agriculture and keep justifying the sustainability of agriculture, and preservation of seeds, and conservation of land. The study is purely based on

theoretical and conceptual based that used primary source of information from Adivasis communities, and their knowledge system that keeps the sustainability of agriculture move on and thus, it helps the rural economy grow, develop, and mobile.

Keywords :- Adivasis Communities, Rural Development, Sustainable Agriculture, Indigenous Knowledge, Adivasis Life.

Introduction :- Odisha stands in an exclusive position among the Indian States and Union Territories for occupying a very big chunk of the population as tribes or Adivasis and colorful tribal scenario. Constitutionally, they come under regions of 5th and 6th schedule areas. Maximum Adivasis people live in hilly and forest regions of the state in a periphery because of which they backward socially, economically, educationally, and healthily. However, they are economically subsistence-oriented, self-reliant within and self-sufficient among them. The community is an unstratified social group that does not fall under the caste structure of Indian society. Although, generally they look like a homogenous social group but they are not, they are a diverse and heterogeneous social group (Xaxa, 1999) having diverse language, folklore, more, beliefs, cultural identity, dialects, customs, traditions, and ceremonies. The social system of Adivasis is simple and their aspirations and needs are not many as compared to mainstream society. They have their own geographical, cultural, political, social, religious, and economic milieu that is so unique and adorable.

There are more than 705 tribal/adivasis communities spread across India according to the census 2011, which constitute about 8.6 percent of the total population of India. These

tribal/ adivasis are seen in three zonal – such as Northeast zonal, Central zonal, and Southern zonal; but Xaxa would classify the tribal in five broad groups- Himalayan regions, Middle regions, Western regions, Southern regions, and Island regions (Xaxa, 2014). In adivasis communities or tribal groupings' Santhals, Gonds, Bhil, and Oraon are numerically strong. As per the constitution of India, there is 75 tribal groups are considered as PVTGs (Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups). But when we see Odisha as a state – it holds 62 tribal/ adivasis communities or groups who speak as many as 74 tribal dialects. As per the census of India (2011), the state of Odisha stands third largest tribal populated state in India who is spread across 30 districts in 314 blocks. They constitute 22.85 percent of the total population of the state and constitute 9.17 percent of the total tribal population of India. These tribal groups have their ethos, ideology, worldview, value orientation, and cultural heritage. Again, they are seen having varieties of activities from collecting forest produced to farming agriculture and from labor work to office work. However, Adivasis are mainly practicing rural economic in different ways- such as nomadic food gathers and hunters, skilled settled agriculture, and horticulture. Thus, there is a diverse socio-economic panorama in adivasis regions of Odisha.

Who are Adivasis ? :- There are ethnic groups who reside peripheries of mainstream society – such as isolated geographically, hill/mountain/forest regions, and river belts. However, it is not realistic –tribes/ adivasis also reside in towns, cities, and metro-cities as well who are well of in social, cultural, political, and economic way (so-called civilized, educated, and modern rationality). Thus, it could be said adivasis, or tribes are everywhere but generally not so – because adivasis believe in collectivism – love to stay together, do daily activities collectively, and celebrate different festivals, ceremonies, functions together. Hence, their presence is felt less in mainstream society and they are isolated. Constitution of India recognized this social group as 'Scheduled Tribes' under the 5th and 6th scheduled areas. By definition tribes or

adivasis is the weaker section that is economically backward; thus there are procedurally included in the tribal groups in the scheduled list under Article 342 of the constitution based on some characteristics – such as primitive traits, distinct culture, geographically isolated, shyness of contact with mainstream society, and economically backwardness. Why these social groups are incorporated in the scheduled list – it is simply to improve the status of the community and protect them from their marginalization and vulnerable conditions and assimilate and integrated them into the mainstream society. The similar protection also extended to Hindu 'lower caste' communities who are historically faced lots of discrimination, stigmatization, and exclusion at the hands of 'upper caste' people. They are called 'scheduled caste' who is also known as dalits and untouchable.

From ancient times, adivasis communities constitute an important segment of Indian society. They live in the forest, hills, and isolated regions. Thus, in an Indian context, they are referred to as indigenous people, scheduled tribes, and ethnic groups. They are commonly known as Adivasis (original settler) in India. They are also known in different names – such as Girijan (hill dwellers), Vanyajati (forest caste men), Adimjati (primitive castes), Janjati (folk communities), and Anusuhit Janjati (Scheduled Tribes). They are socially, educationally, and economically backward classes among the Indian citizens. They are a weaker section of the society, thus they are protected against social injustice and all forms of exploitation as per the constitution of India, article 46. There is no single definition that summarizes tribes or adivasis – defining tribes or adivasis as complex and sophisticated. However, many social scientists, academicians, scholars, and others such as Imperial Gazette, Majumdar, Gillin and Gillin, W. W. Hunter, and others have tried to define it and come to conclude that tribe is not a homogenous social group with a segmentary social structure and territorial affiliation. They have different dialects or languages, simple and adivasis economic which is pre-industrial, their political

institutions are strong and harmonious, they have a specific cultural identity, they maintain social distancing from other communities, castes, and civilized world.

Research Questions and Objectives :- The main research question is, is sustainable agriculture and rural economy possible among Adivasis communities? If 'yes' then –how does it possible among them? How are they able to sustain their rural economy sustainable years after year? How are they protecting, safeguarding, and securing their rights over jal, jungle, and jamin (water, forest, and land)? How their changing pattern of agriculture and type of agriculture is seen and those are sustainable? How their cosmos impact sustainable agriculture and rural economy? How they are procuring, preserving, conserving, and storing the paddy, dals, and other food grains? Is rural economy subsistence and self-sufficient to adivasis communities?

The main research objectives are to study jal, jungle, and jamin as the prime rights over adivasis communities, to see the changing pattern of agriculture and type of agriculture practiced by adivasis, to see the culture and belief based society that is interconnected with their agriculture, livelihood, and life pattern, to look at their preservation pattern of seeds roots, leaves and food grains, to see the simple adivasis' technology and use of manure, to observe modern versus traditional agriculture –benefits and impacts, to see the adivasis' agriculture and the economy as self-sufficiency, and subsistence, to see the rural economy of adivasis as sustainable agriculture that does no harm.

Methods and Techniques :- Following the research questions and objectives, the study follows different sets of methods and techniques – such as to study adivasis communities and their economy as sustainable based on primary sources –visited a community called 'Oraon' who are economically, and socially well. They are self-sufficient and self-reliant in their agriculture. The agriculture they do is mostly a subsistence economy. Again visited tribal communities those

who practice step farming or terrace farming – it is mostly seen in hill or mountain regions to check soil erosion through water current on the slopes. Also visited adivasis communities who practice Jhum cultivation or slash and burn agriculture – it is the process of growing crops by first clearing the land of trees and vegetation and burning them thereafter. Visited adivasis communities who practice shifting cultivation – it an agriculture system in which a person uses a piece of land, only to abandon or alter the initial use a short time later. This system often involves clearing a piece of land followed by several years of wood harvesting or farming until the soil loses fertility. The study uses informal interview in an in-depth way, also follow the case narratively. However, the study is observational to see sustainability in traditional and modern systems of agriculture as well. The study also collected some symbolic images to see how they are so effective in the rural economy and how they are sustaining themselves and agriculture years after year.

Sustainable Adivasis Economy :- Adivasis economy is sustainable, but why it is sustainable, and why other economies are not? Let's understand it by analyzing – adivasis economy is subsistence, self-reliant, and self-sufficient. Adivasis economy depends on varieties of sources –such as forest produce, agriculture, fishing, hunting, and gathering. These are done for individual, group, and community purposes – they do not sell usually, whatever they get from agriculture, forest produce, and another way; they keep for themselves, store them for next year to come and sow them again for production purpose. Adivasis produce crops, vegetables, and other crops for daily use them. In this context, the process, procedure, and pattern followed for agriculture is mostly organic farming (the not modern version of it) where cultivation and other things are done naturally without the help of fertilizer and pesticide (Singh, 2021). Thus, whatever is produced from the field is fresh and good food without pesticides and fertilizer. It keeps human health fit and healthy. It does not affect human health.

But other communities or mostly mainstream society do agriculture for commercial use that's a too commercial crop- such as cotton, oilseeds, cereals, sugarcane, and others. These crops when used heavy dose of chemicals, fertilizers, pesticides, and weedicides for production process – it is not good for living beings on the earth and human beings as well. Here competition spirit is generated among the farmers to produce more food crops for the massive population in the country and profit basis – health is never concerned among them (Ibid.).

Sustainable adivasis economy is not limited to the agricultural sector alone, it is wide – it includes different kinds of farming i.e. fishing, poultry, forest produced, pigs, hens, tendu leaves, mahua flowers and seeds, vegetables, different varieties of dals, and oilseeds.

Adivasis' different Economic Activities :- Adivasis economic is visible when they practices some kinds of economic activities – such as exchange of labor in villages, exchange of things i.e. crops, goats, bulls, hens, pigs, and others. Adivasis are very simple and honest people. They want to live life beautifully without competition. Their economic mentality, thoughts, and ideas are collected and do not have commercial economic activities. They believe in collectivism – thus they have a group and community consciousness. Adivasis are so unique in their way of life, their life itself is a pattern of economic activities. Every adivasi family has its way of sustainable economic activities. Let's see the different economic activities of adivasis in detail with some images.

a. **Collection of Mahua flowers and Seeds :** it is an adivasis economic activity – this mahua flower is collected, dried up, and sell it for economic purposes. From mahua flower, adivasis also extract juice which is alcoholic; from mahua flower, different kinds of adivasis sweets are prepared, mahua flower is having high nutrient values, it is also eatable. Every adivasis family collects it from the jungle. It is an additional income source for them. Adivasis collect mahua seeds as

well – and they crush them for oil. This oil is

used for cooking purposes and ointment for the body.

b. **Tendu Leaves and Fruits :** since adivasis live in the jungle, hilly, and mountain regions where Tendu tree is available. It is another way of income generation for adivasis. They collect the Tendu fruits from the jungle and sell them to the town or nearby villages at

minimum price. When adivasis get more tendu fruits, they dry them and store them safely and use them in the rainy season as their snacks. Furthermore, the government of Odisha and Madhya Pradesh allow the

adivasis to make Beedis, a local cigarette out of the leaves of the tendu tree. It is commercialized in many states of India (Boaz, 2004). The tendu leaf is mostly found in the central zonal where huge adivasis lives. Every year 550 billion pieces of beedis are sold in India, which means it is a very good source of income for adivasis communities but they are cheated, exploited, and not given proper remuneration for their act of collecting the leaves (DownToEarth, 2003). But now the government is taking high GST about 18% on

tendu leaves – it is going to affect the adivasis communities very much (Kukreti, 2017) since it was the economic subsistence for them.

- c. **Fishing in Common** : by meaning and definition adivasis communities live together nearby and have the same likeness, they have their thoughts, feelings, norms, values, customs, and traditions in common. Thus, people living together in a specific geographical area and have a company with each other which reflects when they do

economic activities in common like fishing. They commonly own the pond where they cultivate fishing and commonly catch them and sell them for economic purposes as village society. In a true sense, it gives them a good income source.

- d. **Hunting and Gathering** : in many adivasis communities it is seen as amusement. They collectively go to the jungle a group-wise. There they hunt and gather – such as wild

birds, rabbits, quarrels, and others animals as well and they collect different fruits, roots, and leaves from the jungle collectively. They bring and distribute equally among them all the products whatever they collect from the jungle.

- e. **Char Fruits** : Adivasis collect the Char or Charo (Odia) and sell it in the village hut (market) with a very small amount. It very tasty and natural fruit that keeps the body fit. It is available in hilly, mountain, and jungle only. Those adivasis reside in these

geographical locations only able to collect. The char seeds are collective and remove the upper part and sell it for making biscuits, cookies, chocolate, and others.

- f. **Other economic activities** : there are other economic activities that they practice among the adivasis communities – such as mangoes, borokoli (Odia), guava, orange, tamarind, different vegetables, fruits, roots, and leaves. Thus, the adivasis economy is very much sustainable and self-sufficient.

Varieties of Seasonal Activities of Adivasis :- The list of oilseeds, jungle products, variety of dal that Adivasis cultivate on daily basis. They also practice rice and wheat as their prime agriculture products

Oil Seeds	Jungle Products	Variety of Dals
Rasi (Til in Hindi)	Mahua Seeds and Flowers	Moong Dal – black, green, and white in colors – they are in different size (it is produced during summer and rainy season)
Sun Flowers	Sal Seeds and Flowers	Kulath Dal – black, black & white in colors – they are different in size – some are small and some are big
Sersa	Char	Urad Dal – This dal also called in different names – such as Khuti birhi, Sithari urad (black & white), and Kadua Birhi which is cultivated soon after the cutting paddy and is sown in the wet mud
Jatgi	Kendu/tendu leaves and fruits	Harad Dal

Tici	Makka (Maize)	Channa Dal – it is of two/three varieties
Methi	Gangay	Raisa Dal
Kudrum – variety in color (red, white, and green)	Sweet Potato	Masri Dal
Shanei flowers and seeds	Regular vegetables	
Adivasis also practice agriculture as the main occupation (rice & Wheat)		

Some images of Dal, how it is processed and follow the harvesting it...

Discussion and Analysis :- Reflecting on the above adivasis lifestyle provides some glimpse of sustainability in agriculture that is self-sufficient, self-reliant, and subsistence economy. Adivasis have been practicing agriculture naturally from ages – generation to generation. They keep on improving their standard of lifestyle and agriculture in a simple way. Thus, the adivasis

economy always sustaining every day without losing it.

- a. **Jungle, Jal, and Jamin :** adivasis life is the web of connectivity with these three trinity. They are reciprocal to each other. Every adivasis relate itself and connect with jungle, jal, and jamin. Their identity is with jungle,

jal, and jamin –without which they lose their identity as adivasis. They believe these three as the trinity of the universe which is so powerful in their life. They say it is their gods, goddesses, Marang Buru, Darthi Abbha, Parmeswar, and other names. They connect themselves as it their life, livelihood, savior, protector, and security

- b. **Changing Pattern of Agriculture** : Adivasis are changing as time changing with them. Once upon a time, they were in jungle, hills, mountain top, and river belt. But now they are in cities, villages, and semi-urban places with the mainstream society. Their practice of agriculture started when they were banjati, banbasi, and others in an unstructured way as a migrant. Later, they move to river belts, hills, and mountains where they stay for some time as semi-settled residents and practiced semi-permanent agriculture. Then, they resided in villages where they practiced permanent agriculture. Now it becomes their rural economy through a simple technique and skills.
- c. **Cultural and Belief-based Society** : the adivasis life, agriculture, and jal, jungle, and jamin are reciprocal. Hence, they protect, safeguard, and secure it naturally. Most of the activities are relatable to culture and beliefs. What they believe and what they do are complete to their cosmos.
- d. **Preservation Pattern of Adivasis** : Adivasis communities mostly preserve their seeds, roots, leaves, and food grains every year. They store them in a very good manner. They do sell them whatever extra food grains are with them. Whatever they procure and store are used in next years. This is also used in the form of 'Madait' giving help to others when they are required.
- e. **Types of Agriculture** : a) Step farming or terrace farming – it is mostly seen in hill or mountain regions to check soil erosion through water current on the slopes (Edelstein & Kislev, 1981), b) Jhum cultivation or slash and burn agriculture – it is the process of growing crops by first clearing the

land of trees and vegetation and burning them thereafter (Kleinman et al., 1995), c) Shifting cultivation – it an agriculture system in which a person uses a piece of land, only to abandon or alter the initial use a short time later. This system often involves clearing a piece of land followed by several years of wood harvesting or farming until the soil loses fertility (Conklin, 1961).

- f. **Use of Technology and Use of Manure** : Adivasis rarely use the modern technique for agriculture – they are mostly traditional agriculturist, they use a simple technique, use manure like cow dung (Gobar), leaves, straws
- g. **Rural Economy- Subsistence and Self-sufficiency** : whatever agriculture they do is mostly subsistence, self-reliance, and self-sufficiency. Adivasis never go for a commercial crop. They always practice agriculture as their daily use and whatever extra – foodgrains they get are stored for next years and use for 'Madait' purpose as 'barter system'

Conclusion :- In concluding remarks – it simply indicates the self-sufficiency, self-reliance, rural economic subsistence, and sustainability of adivasis in agriculture. They use manure (that is available naturally like dung from cows, goats, pigs, and hens, compost) rather than fertilizer and pesticide – this means the produced food grains and products are very good for health. Thus, it helps land and soil to become fertile, insects live on earth, and air and crops free from pollution. The crops and food grains possess high nutrient values since it is not adulterated. The crops, dals, and forest produced are stored for next year's cultivation. It simply indicates the sustainable agriculture practice of adivasis. The Adivasis communities also practice the 'Madait System' in different activities which is a learning point for mainstreaming. They also practice the barter system to date. Thus, this kind of adivasis economy always sustaining. Adivasis live their life as simple, they are culturally, socially, and environmentally connected with jal, jungle, and jamin. Thus their pattern of life – provides them a

better life than the rest of the society.

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